

Using LiDAR to assess the influence of fine-scale habitat structure on the abundance of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*)

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Table of Contents

Abstract	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Methodology	7
2.1 Data and model description.....	7
2.2 Workflow.....	10
2.3 Metric selection and data preparation	10
2.4 SDMaps modelling	13
3. Results	14
3.1 Model performance	14
3.2 The role of LiDAR metrics in explaining the density of the bearded reedling	14
3.3 Most important LiDAR metrics for understanding the habitat requirements of the bearded reedling.....	15
3.4 Difference in predictions between models with and without LiDAR metric inclusion	16
4. Discussion	19
4.1 What role do the LiDAR metrics have in explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling?	19
4.2 What are the most important LiDAR metrics for understanding the habitat requirements of the bearded reedling?	19
4.3 To what extent do predictions differ between the inclusion of LiDAR metrics in the model and without?	20
4.4 Future applications and developments	21
4.5 Areas for potential improvement	21
5. Conclusion	22
7. Data storage	23
6. Annex	24
8. Bibliography	34

Abstract

The fine-scale structure of ecosystems is of great importance when considering the distribution of species and level of biodiversity in an area. Collecting fine-scale habitat data with field methods is time consuming and impossible to carry out in a spatially contiguous way and over large spatial extents. This means that current species mapping methods, such as species distribution modelling (SDM), lack data on the fine-scale habitat structure of a species. Advances in remote sensing technology such as LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging), allow for vegetation structure to be measured directly over broad extents and at a high resolution. I investigate the role that LiDAR metrics have on predicting the relative abundance of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*), a reedbed bird of conservation concern, at a national scale. Using habitat-specific LiDAR metrics, I create SDMs to test whether and how fine-scale habitat structure influences the relative abundance of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands, beyond other variables such as land use, soil type and climate data. I found that the LiDAR metrics 'proportion of reed' and 'proportion of water reed' are the most important for understanding the fine-scale habitat requirements of the bearded reedling and rank higher in relative importance than other non-LiDAR covariates. My results showed that the inclusion of LiDAR metrics led to a higher average predicted density of bearded reedlings across the Netherlands, compared to the prediction without LiDAR metrics. These results provide an understanding of how valuable the use of LiDAR data can be for SDM and that it shows great potential for further applications in future modelling approaches. As the bearded reedling is a species of conservation interest in the Netherlands, these results could be beneficial for the future monitoring and protection of the species.

1. Introduction

Effective conservation management requires a thorough understanding of species distribution, and which factors determine this distribution. At broad spatial scales, factors such as climate are thought to be the main drivers of diversity and distribution of terrestrial species (Pearson and Dawson, 2003). However, this is not representative of how species interact directly with their local habitat, and how the 3D habitat structure shapes species distribution on a local scale. Habitat structure is directly influential in the creation and availability of niches for different species, thus influencing both species diversity and composition within a given area (Davies and Asner, 2014). This fine-scale structure of ecosystems has proven to be of great importance when considering the distribution of species and biodiversity in an area (Hewitt *et al.*, 2005). Many studies have shown the relevance of both vertical and horizontal variability of vegetation in understanding how different species use their habitat, and how this drives both the distribution and diversity of species (Bakx *et al.*, 2019; Davies and Asner, 2014). Diversity in vegetation height was first presented as an important factor correlated with an increase in avian diversity in 1961 (MacArthur and MacArthur, 1961). Since then, multiple studies have highlighted the importance of structural vegetation heterogeneity for birds in particular (Müller *et al.*, 2010; Robinson and Holmes, 1984). Despite this knowledge, the fine-scale composition of habitats has mostly been absent from studies that model the distribution of species.

Species Distribution Models (SDMs), sometimes referred to as ecological niche models or habitat models, are a significant factor involved in conservation planning (Austin, 2002). These models are designed either as predictive tools or to better understand the habitat requirements of different species (Vaughan and Ormerod, 2005). They allow for quantitative modelling and mapping of a species' distribution or abundance using species specific environmental and occurrence data (Elith and Leathwick, 2009). These methodologies have been developed and improved over the years and are now central to many areas of research including biogeography, ecology and conservation biology (Araújo and Guisan, 2006). Until recently, the standardisation of SDMs has been lacking, but there are now guides and checklists available to enable proper model reporting and maximise the reproducibility of such modelling approaches (Araújo *et al.*, 2019; Zurell *et al.*, 2020). Climate and land use datasets are the most used variables for SDMs, thought to be the main drivers of species distribution (Pearson and Dawson, 2003). Although usage of these types of data is beneficial in many cases, especially over large spatial extents, it does not take into account the role of habitat structure in species distribution (Koma *et al.*, 2021). As mentioned previously, 3D habitat structure is known to directly influence species distribution and biodiversity (Hewitt *et al.*, 2005), therefore the inclusion of data of this kind in SDMs would be invaluable to improve prediction accuracy and the SDM output. Measuring habitat structure over large spatial scales using field methods is, however, time consuming and impossible to fulfil in a spatially contiguous way (Bakx *et al.*, 2019). This has meant that, until recently, it was not feasible to include fine scale habitat structure when modelling species distribution. Active remote sensing methods, such as Light Detection And Ranging (LiDAR), can provide a solution, allowing for vegetation to be measured directly, over broad extents, at high resolution and in a spatially contiguous way (Davies and Asner, 2014).

Use of LiDAR for ecological applications and habitat modelling is a relatively new concept. This is due to recent advances in LiDAR technology allowing for detailed 3D modelling of animal habitats (Davies and Asner, 2014). LiDAR data collection involves aerial laser altimetry (usually with a drone or other aircraft), where laser pulses are emitted towards the ground, and the time taken for the pulse to return is recorded (Lohani and Ghosh, 2017). These light pulses can penetrate through vegetation layers, providing multiple pulse returns, mapping the 3D structure of a habitat in the form of a point cloud (Davies and Asner, 2014). As the resolution of LiDAR data is so high (< 1 m² resolution), it can be used to provide a detailed picture of the habitat structure of a species (Vierling *et al.*, 2008). LiDAR data allows for the 3D structure of vegetation to be analysed and classified into vegetation metrics. These metrics can be defined by vegetation parameters (e.g. total vegetation, single trees, canopy, understory) and structural type (e.g. cover, height, horizontal variability, vertical variability) (Bakx *et al.*, 2019). By categorising the vegetation in this way, you create a conceptual framework within which ecological LiDAR metrics can be compared. The metrics must also be calculated and extracted from the LiDAR point cloud in order to be used for modelling applications. The

canopy height could, for example, be calculated as the average height of the first returned laser pulses within a defined area - these will be the tallest plants (Ackers *et al.*, 2015; Roll *et al.*, 2015). This information can further our understanding of how species use their habitat at the local scale, and how habitat structure is a driving factor in species abundance and distribution.

Most of the LiDAR-based studies for ecological applications have so far been focussed around birds in forested habitats (Davies and Asner, 2014). This is due to LiDAR being well suited for use within forest habitats, capturing the 3D structure of the canopy layers in detail (Maltamo *et al.*, 2014). Subsequently there is a lack of representation of certain habitat types in ecological applications of LiDAR, such as savannas and wetlands, within the relevant literature (Bakx *et al.*, 2019). LiDAR has, however, been used for mapping within wetlands and reedbed habitats, and has shown to improve the accuracy of vegetation mapping in these environments (Koma *et al.*, 2020; Onojeghuo and Blackburn, 2011). One recent avian study has also looked into the use of LiDAR in wetlands for identifying niche separation and overlap of closely related bird species (Koma *et al.*, 2021). These findings provide evidence that application of LiDAR data in wetlands can be successfully performed and could prove invaluable to the success of future modelling in this habitat. Wetlands provide important habitats for some of the most threatened animal species, many of which rely on the reed for all aspects of their life cycle (Onojeghuo and Blackburn, 2011). Reedbeds are in decline globally and are often subject to intensive anthropogenic management (Malzer, 2017). The lack of ecological research in reedbeds using LiDAR data, and its relevance for conservation, makes it a highly interesting focal habitat for this study.

The bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*) is a wetland bird species and a reedbed specialist. They utilise one species of reed (*Phragmites australis*) for both feeding and breeding, and thus rely on large expanses of reeds and are not found in reedbeds containing trees or shrubs (Malzer, 2017; 'Sovon Vogelonderzoek | Bearded Reedling', 2021). These specific habitat requirements leave them particularly vulnerable to any changes in habitat composition (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). The conservation status of the bearded reedling as a breeding bird in the Netherlands is classed as 'unfavourable' due to annual population variability ('Sovon Vogelonderzoek | Bearded Reedling', 2021), often as a result of harsh winters (Malzer, 2017). Unlike many other wetland bird species within the Netherlands, bearded reedlings are not migratory and stay within the reedbeds year-round. To account for the changes in season, bearded reedlings alter their gut morphology, allowing them to be purely insectivorous during the summer and eat *Phragmites australis* (*P. australis*) seeds throughout the winter months (Malzer, 2017). As the bearded reedling relies on *P. australis* for all aspects of its ecology, reed structure is likely to be a highly influential factor in the relative abundance of the species. Literature shows preferential selection of old, dense areas of reed for nesting, with areas of younger reed commonly selected for foraging (Malzer, 2017; Trnka and Prokop, 2006). Nest location is of greatest priority for this species, and individuals are known to take foraging flights of 400 - 500m on average from their nesting site (Malzer, 2017) to find areas of reed with the greatest food availability (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). However, foraging flights can exceed the average greatly with distances of up to 1000m recorded, which may be related to the distance between dry and wet areas of the reed bed, as bearded reedlings show a preference for feeding in the wettest areas of reed (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). Reed density has also shown to positively affect the abundance of the species during the breeding season (Malzer and Hansell, 2017; Trnka and Prokop, 2006). Bearded reedlings can be highly sensitive to local climatic conditions, with warmer springs allowing for earlier breeding and colder winters resulting in high mortality at a local scale (Malzer, 2017; Malzer and Hansell, 2017).

This study is based on bearded reedling populations in the Netherlands due to the availability of high-quality bird monitoring data at the national scale (from Sovon, the Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology) and data from countrywide LiDAR surveys (AHN). Using Sovon's standardised SDM methodology, I aimed to assess if and to what extent LiDAR data adds to their well tested modelling methodology by running and comparing SDMs both with and without the calculated LiDAR metrics. To meet this aim, I look into the role that LiDAR metrics have on the predicted relative abundance of the bearded reedling at a national scale, assess which LiDAR metrics are of highest relative variable importance and how these compare to the standard land use and climate variables, and the extent to which model predictions differ with and without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics. I expect that:

(H1) LiDAR metrics will have a greater role in explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling than other, commonly used variables (e.g., soil type, land use and climate).

(H2) LiDAR metrics comprising the main habitat of the bearded reedling (reed and water reed) will be the most important when assessing the relative abundance of the species.

(H3) The addition of LiDAR derived metrics to assess the fine-scale habitat structure of the bearded reedling will provide a difference in prediction to the standardised modelling methodology carried out by Sovon.

As the usage of LiDAR data for ecological applications is a relatively new field with a lack of studies on wetlands, and reedbeds in particular, I aim to expand the current knowledge base in this field. The outcome of this research could be beneficial in advising conservation management on how the habitat structure within reedbeds is affecting the distribution of the bearded reedling, a species of conservation interest in the Netherlands.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data and model description

Observation data

The observation data for the bearded reedling is provided by Sovon (Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology) in several different datasets. Sovon carry out a great deal of research to assess developments in numbers and distributions of bird species within the Netherlands and have done so for over 40 years now. The results of their research and data collection help to inform nature policy and management in the Netherlands ('Bird research | Sovon.nl', 2021).

The first dataset provided by Sovon is the bird Atlas field observation data, consisting of 3 data subsets: km² data, 5-minute point counts and 10-minute point counts. For the collection of the bird Atlas data, the Netherlands is split into a 5 x 5 km grid, and within each 5 x 5 km square, eight plots of 1 km² are randomly selected (Figure 1) ('Atlas projects | Sovon.nl', 2021).

Figure 1. Map of the Atlas km squares and buffered survey points in the Netherlands. Points indicate the location of the observer; a standardised buffer is applied to include the area around the observer within which species can be identified. The map shows a zoomed sample of the km squares and survey points in Flevoland and the surrounding area.

Each selected 1 km² plot is surveyed several times throughout both the winter and breeding season for collection of the three data subsets. For both the point count and km² Atlas surveying methodologies, presence and absence of individuals of a species are recorded ('Atlas projects | Sovon.nl', 2021).

The fourth dataset provided by Sovon is the territory mapping data for the breeding monitoring scheme, collected within specific survey plots (Figure 2), referred to as BMP (Breeding Bird Monitoring Project) plots, across the Netherlands ('Breeding bird monitoring (BMP) | Sovon.nl', 2021). Unlike the ATLAS data, this data does not give complete coverage of the country but provides bird observation data with a 10m accuracy within the specific survey

Figure 2. Map of BMP plots used for the bird breeding and monitoring scheme in the Netherlands. The blue polygons show the bearded reedling survey sites for the bird breeding and monitoring scheme. The map shows a zoomed sample of the BMP plots in Flevoland and the surrounding area.

Hoogtebestand Nederland). AHN is an open-source digital elevation file for the whole of the Netherlands, produced using laser altimetry. AHN3 is the most recently collected AHN dataset that is currently available, with all data collected between 2014 and 2019 ('AHN: The making of | AHN', 2021). AHN3 was produced during the 'leaf-off' season of these years and has a high resolution of between 6 - 10 points per square meter ('Kwaliteitsbeschrijving | AHN', 2021).

I did not work with the raw AHN3 LiDAR point cloud but used a LiDAR raster '95th percentile of normalised height' of vegetation in the Netherlands. This raster was created from the AHN3 LiDAR dataset through the eEcoLiDAR project (eScience infrastructure for Ecological applications of LiDAR point clouds) (Kissling *et al.*, 2017), and was calculated at a 10m resolution. The LiDAR point cloud data was processed using 'Laserchicken', a cross-platform Python tool which is user extendable (Meijer *et al.*, 2020). This tool allows for large point cloud datasets to be processed, normalised and filtered for feature calculation ('Welcome to Laserchicken's documentation! — Laserchicken 0.4.2 documentation', 2019). The Laserchicken tool is part of the Laserfarm (Laserchicken Framework for Applications in Research in Macroecology) framework for processing massive LiDAR point cloud datasets ('Welcome to laserfarm's documentation! — laserfarm 0.1.4 documentation', 2020). The '95th percentile of normalised height' raster used in this study was calculated as the '95th percentile of normalised z within 10 m grid cell' (z = height value of LiDAR point), and provides information on vegetation height of the tallest plants, the vertical distribution of vegetation and structural complexity in vegetation layers (Koma *et al.*, 2021).

plots. The surveys carried out for the breeding monitoring scheme involve the counting of breeding pairs of birds, rather than individuals, as is the case for the Atlas data collection.

For both the Atlas and breeding monitoring observation datasets, the plots or points have a unique id by which they can be identified, this will be used for combining all covariate and observation data for the model. A map showing the Sovon official recorded occurrences of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands (combined Atlas and BMP data) can be seen in the Annex (Annex, Figure 15).

LiDAR data

The LiDAR data used in this study is from AHN (Actueel

Other data

Sovon also provided covariate datasets of the Netherlands as well as 1 km and 250 m prediction grids for each of the covariates for use in the model. The covariate datasets also contain information on the area (ha) of each plot/point, and the X and Y coordinate locations. For the Atlas point data, the area of the point is calculated as a standardised buffer around the observer, outside of which they are unlikely to be able to accurately identify specific bird species. The dataset contains data on 80 different covariates including climate, land use, soil, vegetation types, and wetland-specific covariates. Each of the covariates is calculated per Atlas km², observer point, and BMP plot. The description and list of sources from which these covariates were produced are described in the Annex (Annex, Table 1).

The LGN2018 land use data of the Netherlands was provided by the University of Amsterdam for use in this study. The LGN databases are produced annually (since 2018) and use satellite imagery and other data to map the land use of the Netherlands (split into 48 different land use classes) at a resolution of 5 m. Only the wetland and water classes of the LGN2018 dataset were used for analysis in this study (Figure 3). These consist of nine different classes that include

Figure 3. Map of the Netherlands displaying the wetland land classes from the LGN2018 dataset. Legend lists all 9 of the land use types classed as ‘wetland land classes’ that were used in this study.

different wetland vegetation types as well as areas of fresh or saltwater in the Netherlands.

Model description

The SDMaps R package was created by Sovon for the analysis of species abundance and distribution data. SDMs allow for the combination of environmental variables and species observations to create a prediction of distribution or, in the case of this study, species abundance. Due to the large number of variables used in the model, and their often close similarities, there is a high likelihood of multicollinearity between certain variables.

To reduce the risk of multicollinearity, I implemented the ‘ranger’ model algorithm in this study. First presented by Wright and Ziegler in 2017, ‘ranger’ is a random forest model with the faster algorithm provided by the ‘ranger’ R package (Wright and Ziegler, 2017). Random forest is a tree-based, machine-learning classification and regression modelling method that makes very few assumptions, it is also suitable for use with presence-absence observation data (Mi *et al.*, 2017). SDMs that use both presence and absence data perform better than those using presence data only (Barbet-Massin *et al.*, 2012), and as data for both presence and absence of the bearded reedling was provided by Sovon, this is the SDM

approach that I deemed ideal for this study. The `dataExploration()` function was used to calculate Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) to identify and examine variables that have collinearity issues. I chose not to exclude variables with higher collinearity ($VIF > 0.75$), as random forest algorithms are less sensitive to collinearity. Although random forest algorithms tend to suffer less from overfitting than other algorithms (such as a Generalised Linear Model), ten-fold cross validation was carried out to test for overfitting of the data. Moran's I was also calculated to test the spatial autocorrelation of model residuals.

The default settings for the ranger model were used in this study. The default number of regression trees is 500 with a default minimal node size of 5, the default number of variables to split at each node is the (rounded down) square root of the number of variables. Any missing values found in the plot data will be imputed when the model is run, as the ranger model cannot compute with missing covariate values. For spatial interpolation of residuals, the inverse distance weighting (IDW) method was chosen.

2.2 Workflow

Figure 4 below gives a visual overview of the processing steps followed in my methodology. Each of the input data sources and processing steps will be described and explained in greater detail in the following methodology sections. Input data includes both raw and pre-processed data sources that were discussed above in section 2.1 - Data and model description. There are two main data processing steps (Processing bird observation data and Processing LiDAR raster data), followed by the 'Statistical analysis' processing stage, in which the final results are produced.

Figure 4. Workflow diagram of the methodology followed for this study. Legend in top right corner of the figure explains what the different coloured boxes and outlines in the diagram represent. The titled boxes show the three main processing stages carried out (Processing bird observation data, Processing LiDAR raster data, and Statistical analysis), and contain the various steps required for each.

2.3 Metric selection and data preparation

The LiDAR metrics for this study were chosen based on the specific habitat requirements and preferences of the bearded reedling found in literature. We decided upon eight different metrics for use in this study, these are: both the area and proportion of reed, shrubs, trees, and water reed. As a reedbed specialist, the area and proportion of reed are the most obvious choice for this species which, as mentioned previously, relies on reed year-round for both feeding

and breeding (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). As the bearded reedling should be present only in larger areas of reedbed where there are no trees or shrubs present, we also decided to use the area and proportion of shrubs and trees as further variables for use in the modelling. The final two metrics, area and proportion of water reed, were chosen based on evidence in literature that shows water reed is of higher quality and reaches a greater biomass than land reed (Graveland, 1998; Ostendorp, 1993). This is of great relevance in the case of the bearded reedling, as taller, healthier reed will likely produce more seeds, which make up the bulk of the diet for this species during the winter months (Malzer, 2017). The bearded reedling also shows a preference for foraging in areas of water reed over areas of land reed (Beemster *et al.*, 2010).

To prepare my datasets for use in the R SDMmaps package for modelling, several pre-processing steps were required for the various datasets. SDMmaps requires specific input data in order to run a model, these are:

1. Input data on species observations, plot locations (where the observations were made) and covariates (the pre-calculated environmental and land use variables provided by Sovon and the new LiDAR metrics I calculate) in one dataset.
2. Covariate grid maps of predictor variables (for this study, 1km and 250m prediction grid maps were used) and a contour shapefile (a contour shapefile of the Netherlands was used here)
3. Text file with species codes and names (as I was running the model with only one species, this was not necessary)

The model was first run twice without the LiDAR covariates, once with 1km predictor grids and a second time with 250 m prediction grids, so that I had a comparison for my model output predictions. For these two model runs, I only did the observation data preparation – as described in the section below - before running the model. The LiDAR data was then prepared following the LiDAR data preparation section below and added to the other covariates for use in the model. The model could then be run two more times with the addition of the LiDAR covariates, once with 1 km prediction grids and once with 250 m prediction grids.

Observation data preparation

Processing of the bird observation data was carried out in RStudio. As the Atlas point and km² observation datasets contained data for several wetland bird species, I created a subset of the data containing only the species bearded reedling. Any data which fell outside of the years in which the LiDAR data was collected (2014-2019) was removed. The Atlas datasets I then aggregated to the maximum number of bird observations per point (for the 5-minute and 10-minute point count datasets) or km² plot, per year.

The territory mapping data required a similar processing method to the Atlas datasets. I first removed any data outside of the years 2014 – 2019 (years of AHN3 collection) and created a data subset to remove all species other than the bearded reedling (species EU ring number: 13640). The observations were then aggregated to the maximum number of breeding pairs present per BMP plot, per year. Using the 'rbind' function I then combined all the observation datasets into one data frame. This observation data frame could then be directly merged by plot id with the covariate datasets (the BMP plot and Atlas covariate datasets must first be merged into one covariate data frame) for use in the model. Once merged with the covariate data, it is possible to calculate the density of observations per plot.

LiDAR data preparation

The LiDAR raster '95th percentile of normalised height' was first processed using ArcGIS Pro to create the various height rasters. As the bearded reedling is only found within wetlands, the first step was to mask the 95th percentile vegetation height raster with a wetland mask. For the masking, the LGN2018 wetland and water land use classes were used, as many LiDAR vegetation points were also found in areas classed as water. As these points are likely reed vegetation, it was important that we did not exclude this data from the analysis by including only land-based wetland classes. LGN2018 was created in 2018 and is the most recent land use dataset of the Netherlands that could be provided by

the University of Amsterdam for my analysis. The masking removed all vegetation outside of the relevant wetland land classes and additionally reduced the processing time needed for the following steps.

For the required LiDAR metrics (area and proportion of reed, shrubs, trees and water reed), three different height ranges were selected. These were, 1-3 m for reed based upon reed canopy height under optimal hydrological conditions (Onojeghuo and Blackburn, 2011), 3-6 m for shrubs and 6-30 m for trees. After the application of the wetland mask to the LiDAR raster, there were still biases present (outliers of up to 179 m in height) due to bridges, powerlines, and other man-made artefacts. To further clean the data and eliminate non-vegetation data points, 30 m was chosen as the upper height limit for trees. Tree species commonly found in wetlands such as Poplars (*Populus*), Lindens (*Tilia*), and Willows (*Salix*), rarely reach heights of more than 30 m, with average heights for these species falling between 25-30 m (Goudzwaard, 2021). Using the 'Raster Calculator' tool in ArcGIS Pro, I then calculated the different height layers from the masked 95th percentile height raster. I was left with three separate rasters, one for each of the height classes: 1-3 m reed, 3-6 m shrubs, 6-30 m trees.

To identify the final LiDAR metric, water reed was extracted from the 1-3 m reed raster. To do this, I extracted the water land classes (freshwater and saltwater) from the LGN2018 wetland and water land use raster, using the 'Select by Attributes tool' in ArcGIS Pro, and exported this selection to a new raster layer. To distinguish land reed from water reed, I decided that a buffer of 20m should be applied to the water land class of the LGN2018 dataset. The buffer size of 20m was deemed ideal to ensure water reed which grows in shallow coastal areas or where there may be seasonal water inundation and flooding was also extracted for the 'water reed' metric. Any vegetation points falling within the water land class could then be included as well as any vegetation within 20 meters of the water. This accounts for varying levels of water inundation across different months and / or years, which can subsequently affect the quality of the reed and its classification as either water or land reed (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). I used the 'Buffer' tool to apply a buffer of 20m to the extracted water land use class. Using the 'Clip Raster' tool, I then clipped the 1-3m reed raster to the extent of the buffered water polygon. The output raster was classed as water reed (1-3m in height).

In order to calculate the zonal statistics for each of the four LiDAR metric rasters (reed, shrubs, trees and water reed) I used QGIS, as it can better calculate zonal statistics for overlapping polygons than ArcGIS. The zonal statistics were calculated for three different polygon shapefiles: Atlas km squares grid and buffered points, bearded reedling BMP plots, and a 250m grid of the Netherlands. The zonal statistics from the 250m grid polygon was used to create prediction grids for the model at a 250m resolution. To calculate the area and proportion of reed within the various polygons, the count of pixels per polygon was needed. Using the 'Zonal Statistics' tool, I selected one of the four raster layers (e.g., 1-3m reed) and one of the three vector layers containing zones (e.g., Atlas km squares grid and buffered points) as the input layers and selected 'Count' as the statistics to be calculated and ran the tool. I then repeated this step, with 1-3m reed raster again but with the BMP plots selected as the vector layer containing zones, and a third time with the 250m grid of the Netherlands. This process was replicated for each of the four LiDAR metric rasters. Once complete, the attribute tables of the three shapefiles (Atlas km squares grid and buffered points, BMP plots, and 250m grid of the Netherlands) each contained four new columns with the count of reed, shrub, tree, and water reed pixels per polygon.

From the Atlas km squares and buffered points and BMP plots database files, I could calculate the area and proportion metrics for use as variables in the model. The database files were imported into RStudio where the area metrics were first calculated. The resolution of the LiDAR metric rasters is 10m, meaning that each pixel is 10 x 10m (or 100m²). The area of reed, shrub, trees and water reed could therefore be calculated as the count of pixels per polygon, multiplied by 100 (this gave the area in m²). As all other covariates provided by Sovon to be included in the model were calculated per hectare, the calculated area per polygon was divided by 10,000 to give the area in hectares. I merged the area metrics with the respective covariate datasets provided by Sovon, as these contained information on the area (in ha) of each polygon / buffered point. Once merged, I could calculate the proportion of reed, shrubs, trees and water reed per survey point or polygon by dividing the area of these metrics by the area of the polygons / buffered points. Finally,

all Atlas and BMP covariate data was merged into one covariate dataset which now contained eight LiDAR variables: area and proportion of reed, shrub, tree, and water reed.

I also produced ascii covariate grids and png files in RStudio, at 250m and 1km resolution, for all eight of the LiDAR metrics for use in the model. These were added to the respective '1kmgrid' and '250mgrid' folders that the model calls from, after first running the models without the LiDAR metrics included.

2.4 SDMaps modelling

The input data was first read into RStudio and converted into an object using the `data2SDMaps()` function. This object can be directly used for a modelling run or saved for use at a later point and loaded into the R workspace. The function `SDMaps()` has many argument possibilities to define the various steps for the model to follow. First it is necessary to describe the model type to be used, the type of data I am using, and arguments for dealing with spatial autocorrelation. As the data I use are continuous and have a lower boundary of 0, I indicated the data type as 'density' to the model. `SDMaps()` creates file outputs that include predictions for the plot locations per species, model residuals, map visualisations, cross validations, results of variable selections and model-specific information.

After the model run was complete, running the command `SDMapsSummary()` allows for further information on the modelling success and parameter estimates to be produced. In this stage, I was able to calculate the variable importance, produce variable importance plots, and partial dependence plots for the 10 most important variables, as well as calculating and producing a Moran's I plot to test for spatial autocorrelation.

Investigating the role of LiDAR metrics in explaining bearded reedling abundance

To investigate the influence that LiDAR metrics have on explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands and test my first hypothesis, I produced partial dependence plots. The partial dependence function plots the change in the average predicted value as specified covariates vary over their marginal distribution, generating something resembling a response curve. These plots allow for investigation into the relationship between particular variables and the density of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands, to see if there is a linear or more complex relationship occurring. I generated plots for all eight LiDAR covariates used in the second model, and eight plots of the non-LiDAR covariates of highest relative importance (as determined by the model) from the first model. This allows me to compare the LiDAR metrics dependence plots with those of the non-LiDAR metrics to see whether LiDAR metrics have a greater role in explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling than other, commonly used variables.

LiDAR metric importance

In order to assess the role of the calculated LiDAR metrics in explaining bearded reedling density across the Netherlands and test my second hypothesis, I produced variable importance plots. The variable importance plot output is restricted to a max of 30 covariates. The algorithm estimates the importance by looking at how much prediction error increases when data for a given variable is permuted while all others are left unchanged. The necessary calculations are carried out tree by tree during forest construction. `SDMaps` does not display the original measure of variable importance but translates it into a relative measure.

Differences in model predictions

The model was first run two times without the LiDAR covariates, once with 1km predictor grids and a second time with 250m predictor grids, so that I had a comparison for my model output predictions to test my third hypothesis. As output, the model provides a species prediction map, a map of interpolated residuals and a map with predictions + interpolated residuals. These maps provide a visualisation of the predicted species abundance that can then be used to compare model predictions with and without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics. As the Netherlands is such a large area, visual comparison to see what the differences in predicted abundance are is not easy to see just by looking between the maps. Using ArcGIS Pro, I adjusted the colour scales and legends of the different maps so that they are directly comparable.

3. Results

3.1 Model performance

Both models performed well with rather similar results overall. Ten-fold cross validation of model 1 (without LiDAR metrics included) explained 78.27% of the variance and model 2 (with LiDAR metrics included) explained 78.52% of the variance. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was higher for model 1 (MAE = 0.175) than for model 2 (MAE = 0.165), and the Spearman's correlation factor was lower for model 1 (corr = 0.305) than in model 2 (corr = 0.325). Moran's I statistic of the model residuals for both models 1 and 2 showed no spatial autocorrelation of residuals, although there was some underestimation (Annex, Figure 10 and 11). Full statistics tables for both models, with cross-validation results, are available in the Annex (Annex, Table 2 and 3).

3.2 The role of LiDAR metrics in explaining the density of the bearded reedling

The partial dependence plots show individual variables plotted against the model prediction after considering the average effects of other covariates in the model. They do not account for individual interactions between the variables but provide a visualisation of the effects of the variables on the predictions of the model.

Figure 5 shows the partial dependence plots for all eight of the LiDAR metrics used in model 2. In the plots showing the proportion of reed (*lidar_reed_proportion*) and proportion of water reed (*lidar_water_reed_proportion*), the density of bearded reedlings increases with an increasing proportion of reed per survey plot. There is a clear relationship shown in these plots, and out of the eight different LiDAR covariates (Figure 5), these two most clearly

Figure 5. Partial dependence plots for all eight LiDAR metrics included in model 2. The X-axis shows the selected variable, with the relative variable importance (%) below, the Y-axis (yhat) shows the model predicted density of the bearded reedling. The blue lines visible on the X-axis show the distribution of the available covariate data in 10% quantiles.

explain the density of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands. For the area of reed (*lidar_reed_area*) and area of water reed (*lidar_water_reed_area*) plots, the density of bearded reedlings increases rapidly with the presence of reed but then plateaus at a density of approximately 1.5 (*lidar_reed_area*) and 1.35 (*lidar_water_reed_area*) respectively, showing that the presence of reed or water reed is necessary for there to be bearded reedlings present, but implies that a further increase in reed area does not result in an increased density of bearded reedlings. The shrub area (*lidar_shrub_area*), tree area (*lidar_tree_area*) and tree proportion (*lidar_tree_proportion*) plots don't show a bearded reedling density above 0.3, which confirms my expectations from literature, that these habitat types are not used by

the bearded reedling. A shrub proportion (lidar_shrub_proportion) of 0.4 – 0.5 however, shows a sudden increase to a bearded reedling density of 1, suggesting that at a proportional shrub cover of ~0.5, we would be more likely to see occurrence of bearded reedlings. This particular plot (lidar_shrub_proportion) does not match my expected results as a higher proportion of shrubs should result in a decrease in bearded reedling density, rather than an increase.

Comparing the results in Figure 5 to those in Figure 6 below, we see that these eight non-LiDAR covariates from the first model (run without LiDAR metrics) show a similar relationship to bearded reedling density as the reed related LiDAR metrics shown in Figure 5. Reed related variables (Riet_area_perc, Eco_moeras_riet, SNL_riet_overjarig, Riet_omtrekdh) show a positive relationship with bearded reedling density, as the amount of reed increases. The 'Riet_area' covariate also shows a comparable relationship to that seen in Figure 5 in the 'lidar_reed_area' plot, but here we see a higher maximum predicted density of bearded reedlings (~2.5 compared to ~1.5). Marshland related covariates (Ecoh_moeras, CBShfd_2012_Moeras) and openness covariate (openheid2009_mean) also show a positive relationship with bearded reedling density.

Figure 6. Partial dependence plots of the eight covariates with the highest relative importance for predicting the density of the bearded reedling, from model 1 - run without LiDAR metrics. The X-axis shows the selected variable, with the relative variable importance (%) below, the Y-axis (yhat) shows the model predicted density of the bearded reedling. The blue lines visible on the X-axis show the distribution of the available covariate data in 10% quantiles. Further information on each of the displayed covariates can be found in the Annex in Table 1 (Annex, Table 1).

3.3 Most important LiDAR metrics for understanding the habitat requirements of the bearded reedling

The variable importance plots produced in the model summary, allow for comparison of the relative variable importance between the model run with and without LiDAR metric inclusion. The variable importance plots for the ranger modelling technique displays only the 30 most important variables in a dot chart, the importance of all variables sums up to 100%. This gives us an objective overview of all covariates included in the model.

Figure 7 shows that the variable with the highest relative importance in the second model is the proportion of reed (lidar_reed_proportion), with a relative variable importance (RVI) of 13%. The proportion of water reed (lidar_water_reed_proportion) has the second highest RVI of 7.6%. The next LiDAR variables of interest here, both with a RVI of 2.8%, include the area of reed (lidar_reed_area) and area of water reed (lidar_water_reed_area), both

of which rank in the top 10 of variables of relative importance. This confirms my expected results, that the LiDAR variables comprising the main habitat of the bearded reedling (reed and water reed) will be of highest RVI.

The proportion of shrub (lidar_shrub_proportion) with a RVI of 1.3% and area of shrub (lidar_shrub_area) with a RVI of 1%, are also present in the top 30 variables displayed in Figure 7 (ranked 20th and 29th), but do not have a significant impact on the model prediction, as they are of similar RVI to the other covariates. The two tree-related LiDAR covariates (lidar_tree_area, lidar_tree_proportion) do not feature in the 30 variables of highest RVI, and do not have a significant impact on the model's prediction of bearded reedling density. This further

Figure 7. Relative variable importance plot (%) for model 2, run with the inclusion of LiDAR metrics. Displaying the 30 most important variables (Y-axis) for predicting the relative abundance of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*), with the model-calculated relative variable importance of each covariate (X-axis), ranked highest to lowest.

confirms my expected results, as trees and shrubs should not be present in bearded reedling habitat and are therefore not important when predicting the density of the species. The RVI plot for model 1, run without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics, can be viewed in the Annex (Annex, Figure 12).

3.4 Difference in predictions between models with and without LiDAR metric inclusion

The prediction map outputs from the different model runs allow for a visual comparison between the models run with and without the calculated LiDAR metrics as input variables. The prediction maps were calculated and displayed at both a 1 km and 250 m resolution.

The prediction maps (Figure 8 and 9) show a great difference in the predicted density of bearded reedlings in the Netherlands when LiDAR metrics are included in the model predictions, compared to the prediction maps created by model 1. Overall, the inclusion of LiDAR metrics in the model seems to increase the predicted density of bearded

reedlings across the Netherlands. The 1 km prediction map produced without LiDAR metrics (Figure 8a) predicts a maximum density of 26 whereas the 1 km prediction map produced with the inclusion of LiDAR metrics (Figure 8b) has a higher maximum density of 30. Overall, the LiDAR 1 km prediction map shows a higher average predicted density (mean = 4.61) than the 1 km prediction map (mean = 0.07).

Figure 8. Bearded reedling density prediction maps of the Netherlands at a resolution of 1 km without (a) and with (b) the inclusion of LiDAR metrics as variables in the model. The colour legend indicates the predicted density of bearded reedlings per 1 km grid square.

The 250 m prediction map produced without LiDAR metrics (Figure 9a) predicts a maximum density of 25 and mean density of 0.08. The LiDAR 250 m prediction map (Figure 9b) shows a higher maximum predicted density of 35, with a mean density of 1.2. The average predicted density between the 250 m predictions (difference of 0.4) are more similar

Figure 9. Bearded reedling density prediction maps of the Netherlands at 250 m resolution without (a) and with (b) the inclusion of LiDAR metrics as variables in the model. The colour legend indicates the predicted density of bearded reedlings per 250 m grid square.

than those in the 1 km prediction maps (difference of 4.54). These results confirm my expectation that the prediction maps created with the inclusion of LiDAR metrics will show a difference in bearded reedling predicted density in the Netherlands. This difference is greater than expected however, as the maps (Figure 8b and 9b) show very few areas with a predicted density of 0, and the species should only occur in wetland areas containing reed. The LiDAR maps (Figure 8b and 9b) show high predicted densities around rivers and other areas of water (see Figure 3 for fresh and salt water in the Netherlands). The highest densities for the LiDAR 250 m and 1 km prediction maps, 15 - 35 and 15 - 30 respectively, are situated in areas known to have large populations of bearded reedlings such as the Oostvaardersplassen (Annex, Figure 13 and 14). As the proportion of reed and water reed LiDAR covariates had such a high RVI in the model (Figure 7), the covariate grids for these two metrics will have been most drawn upon for use in the prediction mapping for the bearded reedling. This would have contributed to the greater bearded reedling densities seen in Figure 8b and 9b, when compared to the predictions without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics shown in Figure 8a and 9a.

4. Discussion

This study shows the influence of habitat-specific LiDAR metrics in predicting the abundance of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands when integrated into a well-tested SDM approach. Using countrywide LiDAR (AHN3) data and high-quality presence-absence bird monitoring data (Sovon) for my analysis, I found that the LiDAR metrics 'proportion of reed' and 'proportion of water reed' are the most important for understanding the fine-scale habitat requirements of the bearded reedling and rank higher in relative importance than other non-LiDAR covariates. My results show that the inclusion of LiDAR metrics leads to a higher average predicted density of bearded reedlings across the Netherlands, compared to the prediction without LiDAR metrics.

4.1 What role do the LiDAR metrics have in explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling?

The partial dependence plots of the LiDAR covariates show that the relative abundance of the bearded reedling can be best explained by reed related variables – reed and water reed. Water reed was an additional variable that I chose to include based upon literature indicating the importance of water reed in the provision of food for the species throughout the year (Graveland, 1998; Ostendorp, 1993). The LiDAR partial dependence plots for tree area and proportion and shrub area showed no strong positive or negative relationship to bearded reedling density, and all show predicted densities of <0.3. Despite no strong correlation being shown, the plots indicate that there will be no bearded reedlings in the presence of trees or shrubs. This further strengthens the argument in literature that reed is the sole most important vegetation type for the bearded reedling (Malzer, 2017; Onojeghuo and Blackburn, 2011). The shrub proportion plot presented a surprising result with 50% shrub coverage showing a bearded reedling density of 1. As the occurrence of bearded reedlings in areas of extensive shrub cover is highly unlikely based on their habitat preferences, it could be that some areas classified as shrub (3-6 m height) are actually expanses of tall reed. It is possible under the right conditions for reed to exceed heights of 3 m (Poulin *et al.*, 2010), especially with water reed as it often has a higher biomass than land reed (Graveland, 1998; Ostendorp, 1993). This is potentially something that can be investigated in future studies with a better distinction between wetland and non-wetland vegetation types.

The proportion of reed and water reed LiDAR metrics provide a clear indication that an increased proportion of reed and water reed will result in a higher abundance of bearded reedlings. This aligns with research on the habitat preferences of the bearded reedling, indicating presence of reed as the most important factor for this species (Beemster *et al.*, 2010; Malzer, 2017; Malzer and Hansell, 2017). When compared to the non-LiDAR covariates however, we also see a similar relationship with reed and wetland related covariates in explaining bearded reedling abundance. Although the LiDAR proportion of reed and water reed covariates provide a clear explanation of the relative abundance of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands, they do not provide a clearer explanation than the most important (as determined by the model) non-LiDAR covariates (Figure 6). This means that H1 - LiDAR metrics will have a greater role in explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling than other, commonly used variables - will be rejected. Nevertheless, these results show that use of fine-scale habitat metrics for modelling the distribution of the bearded reedling can assist in explaining the abundance of the species at a national scale and have great potential for applications in future studies. LiDAR derived covariates should therefore be used alongside other covariates in SDMs, not replace them completely.

4.2 What are the most important LiDAR metrics for understanding the habitat requirements of the bearded reedling?

The results of this study show that the reed and water reed LiDAR metrics were the most important LiDAR metrics for explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands. This confirms H2 - LiDAR metrics comprising the main habitat of the bearded reedling (reed and water reed) will be the most important when assessing the relative abundance of the species. Studies show that reed is the most important habitat type for the bearded reedling as it relies upon it year-round for breeding and feeding (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). In particular, the proportion

of reed and proportion of water reed were the two most important metrics for the model in predicting the density of the species, with the areas of reed and water reed ranked the 7th and 8th most important variables respectively. As water reed usually has a higher biomass than land reed, it will likely produce more seed and therefore be an important source of food for the bearded reedling during the winter months (Graveland, 1998; Ostendorp, 1993). My model results also reflect this, with the LiDAR metrics proportion of reed and water reed being the two variables with the highest relative importance in predicting the density of bearded reedlings. As the covariates which ranked 3rd – 6th in RVI are also reed-related variables, the LiDAR area of reed and water reed covariates therefore provide further evidence of the importance of reed detection when investigating the density of the bearded reedling.

The proportional LiDAR reed and water reed metrics were of greater importance to the model than the area of reed and water reed. This is likely because bearded reedlings prefer expanses of reed that do not contain other vegetation types such as trees and shrubs, but rather contains only reed (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). The LiDAR shrub and tree area and proportion metrics did not show a high relative variable importance for predicting the density of the bearded reedling. This result was expected as, mentioned above, research shows the species will only nest in large expanses of reed that are free of shrubs and trees (Beemster *et al.*, 2010). It is interesting that these metrics did not present a negative correlation with bearded reedling density, but rather showed no relationship at all.

4.3 To what extent do predictions differ between the inclusion of LiDAR metrics in the model and without?

There is a large difference shown between the prediction maps with and without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics in the model. This could be due to the LiDAR variables giving a more detailed depiction of the vegetation within wetlands, thus providing a greater range of potential habitats if more reed vegetation is detected. The prediction maps created with the LiDAR variables (Figures 8 and 9) indicate a much wider distribution of bearded reedlings throughout the Netherlands than is currently recorded in the observation data provided by Sovon (Annex, Figure 15). Evidence supporting the predicted larger distribution of bearded reedlings can be found by looking at citizen science observations of the bearded reedling. This can be visualised on the website of Waarneming.nl ('Bearded Reedling - *Panurus biarmicus*', 2021) where you can sort the observations by year and view them on a 1 km resolution map (Annex, Figure 16). The inaccessibility of many reedbeds due to reed density and water inundation, as well as the bearded reedling being an elusive species which stays low in the reeds, makes accurate measurement of species abundance and distribution quite challenging (Malzer, 2017). The largest populations of bearded reedlings can be seen in the autumn after the breeding season, where they tend to fly higher above the reeds in large flocks as the juveniles begin to disperse (Surmacki and Stępniewski, 2003). This is where citizen science can be beneficial in providing observations at times of the year where official surveys may not be taking place (e.g., outside of the breeding season) and in different locations, thus giving a more complete picture of the abundance and distribution of the species throughout the year (McCaffrey, 2005). New areas not previously surveyed for bearded reedling presence, should therefore be considered as potential habitat for the bearded reedling and could be surveyed in the future.

Another potential reason for this larger predicted density is that the LiDAR metrics are calculated per survey plot or point, which could cause the model to overestimate bearded reedling density in certain areas, as it does not take the metrics in the surrounding plots into account. The bearded reedling is found in larger areas of reed, often flying 500m or further for foraging (Malzer, 2017), it is thus likely that calculating the metrics per km square survey plot will divide bearded reedling ranges into separate plots. It would be interesting in future studies to calculate the LiDAR metrics in relation to the total area of the LGN2018 wetland classes. Calculating the area and proportion of the metrics per survey point / plot does not consider the metrics in surrounding plots and this could be better quantified by considering wetlands as a whole.

The higher density predictions found outside of areas where observations have occurred are most often along waterways throughout the country, sometimes occurring where there are no recorded wetland areas. Although generally the species prefers larger areas of reed (Malzer, 2017), some studies suggest that outside of the breeding season, bearded reedlings inhabit smaller, drier areas of reed (Surmacki and Stępniewski, 2003). It is also possible that by including all areas of water in the Netherlands as a mask when creating the LiDAR metrics, that non-wetland vegetation types such as grasses, tall weeds and woody vegetation falling between 1-3m in height (Alexander *et al.*,

2015), may have been classified as reed in the height categorisation process. Alternative methods could be used for calculating the reed and water reed metrics in future studies to avoid inclusion of non-wetland vegetation. The wetland mask used in this study included all areas of fresh and salt water in the Netherlands (Figure 3) to ensure no reed was missed in the calculation, as many of the LiDAR 95th percentile height raster vegetation points also fell within areas classed as water in the LGN2018 map. Subsequently, any vegetation of 1-3 m in height around waterways was included in the height class raster calculations. Future studies could choose to only include areas of water that occur in / within a specified radius of known areas of wetland vegetation or areas of marshland.

4.4 Future applications and developments

As this study only used the pre-calculated 95th percentile height raster created by the eEcoLiDAR project, there is still the possibility to create a greater range of LiDAR metrics for inclusion as variables in the model. Re-sampling of the original LiDAR data could allow for analysis at a higher resolution (original AHN data is available at 0.5m resolution) (AHN, 2021), further improving the accuracy of the data on 3D vegetation structure within wetlands. For future assessments of bearded reedling density, tree and shrub related LiDAR metrics could be excluded, with the focus more on developing different reed-related LiDAR metrics.

The results of this study show that reed-related LiDAR variables are the most important when investigating the density of bearded reedlings in the Netherlands. The 95th percentile height raster used in this study provides data on the vertical distribution of vegetation, but there are other calculated LiDAR vegetation metrics that could be used to further examine this relationship. The density and horizontal structure of the reed is another factor of great importance for the bearded reedling, it prefers denser reed for nesting and nest predation has been shown to decline with increasing stem density in reedbeds (Malzer and Hansell, 2017). By including the variable 'water reed', we did consider the importance of reed density - typically water reed is taller and more dense than land reed (Graveland, 1998; Ostendorp, 1993) - and tried to include it to some extent. This is, however, something that could be investigated in greater detail using height thresholds, vertical variability and measures such as the density of vegetation below 2 m in height, as recent studies show that these metrics are useful for the separation of the two reed types (Koma *et al.*, 2020). Further LiDAR metrics such as the pulse penetration ratio (a measure of vegetation cover) and variance of the digital surface model (a measure of horizontal variability) (Koma *et al.*, 2020) could be included in future studies investigating which reed-related LiDAR metrics can best predict the density of the bearded reedling.

4.5 Areas for potential improvement

The Atlas bird observation data that was available for use in this study only spanned until 2016, meaning I could only use two years' worth of Atlas data (2014 - 2016) that aligned with the AHN3 collection years (2014 - 2019) ('AHN: The making of | AHN', 2021). Using more up to date bird monitoring information could be beneficial for future studies to ensure the most accurate picture of known bearded reedling abundance across the Netherlands is accounted for.

There is a mismatch in the data collection time periods for the bird observation data and the LiDAR data. Observation data is collected throughout the breeding seasons ('Atlas projects | Sovon.nl', 2021; 'Breeding bird monitoring (BMP) | Sovon.nl', 2021), while AHN LiDAR data is collected in the leaf-off season which runs between December and March ('AHN: The making of | AHN', 2021). This is due to its main use being for digital terrain mapping of the Netherlands. Although long woody stems of reed do remain through the winter, the other reed vegetation dies back (Malzer, 2017), meaning the land reed is rather sparse in the winter months. This could make detection by the laser pulses more difficult, giving a less accurate depiction of the reed vegetation than is seen in the breeding season and throughout the summer. Although this difference in data collection time periods is somewhat mitigated by the bearded reedling being a non-migratory species and present year-round in the reedbeds (Malzer, 2017), use of LiDAR data collected during leaf-on periods could be a solution to provide a better picture of the vegetation present, particularly in wetlands where the vegetation is generally lower and more open (Alexander *et al.*, 2015). Currently, leaf-on collection of LiDAR data is not something that is carried out at a national scale in the Netherlands but could be useful in future ecological applications of LiDAR.

5. Conclusion

The use of LiDAR data in SDM shows great success in providing a detailed insight into how the fine-scale structure of a species' habitat influences their relative abundance. Using Sovon's standardised SDM methodology, I assessed if and to what extent LiDAR data adds to their methodology by running and comparing SDMs for the bearded reedling both with and without the calculated LiDAR metrics. I found that the LiDAR metrics 'proportion of reed' and 'proportion of water reed' rank higher in relative importance than other non-LiDAR covariates and are the most important LiDAR metrics for understanding the fine-scale habitat requirements of the bearded reedling. The LiDAR metrics did not, however, have a greater role in explaining the relative abundance of the bearded reedling than the non-LiDAR covariates, as many of the non-LiDAR reed-related variables showed a similar relationship. My results showed that the inclusion of LiDAR metrics led to a higher average predicted density of bearded reedlings across the Netherlands, compared to the prediction without LiDAR metrics. Overall, the usage of LiDAR metrics for SDM in this study was successful and provides further evidence for the benefits of ecological applications of LiDAR. The results of this project could be used to advise conservation management on wetland areas within the Netherlands. As the bearded reedling is a species of conservation interest in the Netherlands, these results could be beneficial for the future monitoring and protection of the species. The framework in this study could also be applied to other reed dwelling bird species, increasing our knowledge of how individual species utilise the fine-scale structure of their habitats and how this drives their distribution at the local scale. My results provide an understanding of how valuable the use of LiDAR data can be for SDM and that it shows great potential for further applications in future modelling approaches. The use of countrywide LiDAR data for analysing wetland habitat structure provides new insight into its applicability for modelling a variety of different habitat types other than forests, at a national scale. Finally, there is the possibility for future up-scaling of the project to apply the methodologies proposed in this study to bearded reedling density in other countries, as well as different species within wetlands.

7. Data storage

In order to comply with the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability), I have shared my scripts and thesis via a community I have created on Zenodo.org. The community is called “Using LiDAR to assess the influence of fine-scale habitat structure on the abundance of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*)”, and can be found at <https://zenodo.org/communities/lidar-fine-scale-habitat-assessment/?page=1&size=20>. The RStudio scripts used for data preparation (e.g. aggregation and cleaning of bird observation data, production of 250 m and 1 km LiDAR covariate prediction grids) and modelling in this study, as well as the SDMaps package that’s available from the Sovon website have been shared through this community. It was not possible to upload the original data used in this study, as it was provided to me by Sovon and the University of Amsterdam, and not collected by me directly from open-source data platforms. The R package SDMaps that was used for creating and running the SDMs in this study is openly available to download from the Sovon website, along with a manual and examples (‘SDMaps | Sovon.nl’, 2021). While my study cannot be replicated without the use of my original data, with the methodologies and scripts provided the modelling process can be used for other similar studies when the appropriate input data is used.

6. Annex

Table 1. List of covariates provided by Sovon for use in this study. These variables are used by Sovon when modelling wetlands, so include many wetland-related land use covariates. Each covariate is classified into a category (first column) and the covariate names provided (second column) show the names as used in the model. The covariate descriptions (third column) are translated from the Dutch list of descriptions provided by Sovon, into English. Source(s) show where the covariates were downloaded from or from what datasets they were then calculated (fourth column).

Data type as classified by Sovon	Covariate names	Description	Source(s)
Bioclimatic	bioclim_ann_precip bioclim_max_temp_warmest_month bioclim_mean_ann_temp bioclim_mean_diurnal_range bioclim_min_temp_coldest_month bioclim_precip_driest_month bioclim_precip_seasonality bioclim_temp_ann_range	Annual precipitation (1x1 km) Maximum temperature in the hottest month (1x1 km) Average annual temperature (1x1 km) Average daily temperature difference (1x1 km) Minimum temperature in the coldest month (1x1 km) Precipitation in the driest month (1x1 km) Seasonal variations in precipitation (1x1 km) Annual temperature difference (1x1 km)	Based on WorldClim - global climatic data for ecological modeling and GIS Worldclim.org
Soil	Bodem_klei_licht Bodem_klei_op_veen Bodem_klei_op_zand Bodem_klei_zwaar Bodem_leem Bodemhfd_Klei Bodemhfd_Kleiopveen Bodemhfd_Leem Bodemhfd_Veen Bodemhfd_Zand	Cover with soil type 'Light clay' (1x1 km) Cover with soil type 'Clay on peat' (1x1 km) Cover with soil type 'Clay on sand' (1x1 km) Cover with soil type 'Heavy clay' (1x1 km) Cover with soil type 'Loam' (1x1 km) Cover with main soil type 'Clay' (1x1 km) Cover with main soil type 'Clay on peat' (1x1 km) Cover with main soil type 'Loam' (1x1 km) Cover with main soil type 'Peat' (1x1 km) Cover with main soil type 'Sand' (1x1 km)	Derived from the soil map of the Netherlands (Bodemkaart 1\;50 000)
Land use	CBSHfd_2012_Bos CBSHfd_2012_Industrieterr CBSHfd_2012_Landbouw CBSHfd_2012_Moeras CBSHfd_2012_Recreatie_en_park CBSHfd_2012_Weg_en_spoor CBSHfd_2012_Woongebied CBSHfd_2012_Zoet_water CBSHfd_2012_Zout_water	Forest Industrial site Agricultural area Swamp and wet natural terrain Recreation site Road and rail Residential area Freshwater Saltwater	Based on the Soil Use File (2012) from the CBS (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek) (https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/dossier/nederland-regional/geographical-data/nature-and-environment/file-soil-use)
Main - ecotopes	Ecoh_bebouwing Ecoh_bos Ecoh_grasland Ecoh_heide_hoogveen Ecoh_kwelders Ecoh_open_duin Ecoh_open_zand Ecoh_water Ecoh_moeras	Coverage by main ecotope 'Buildings' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Forest' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Grassland' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'moorland' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Salt marshes' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Open dune' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Open sand' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Water' (1x1 km) Coverage by main ecotope 'Swamp' (1x1 km)	Based on chapter 4.1.2 in Pouwels et al. 2006, Adaptation LARCH, Customization in species models. Statutory Research Tasks Nature and Environment, WOt report 23, available at W:\Gis\Ecotopen.
Sub - ecotopes	Eco_moeras_overig Eco_moeras_riet Eco_moeras_ruigte	Coverage by sub-ecotope 'Other swamp' (1x1 km) Coverage by sub-ecotope 'Reed Swamp' (1x1 km) Coverage by sub-ecotope 'Swamp rough' (1x1 km)	Based on chapter 4.1.2 in Pouwels et al. 2006, Adaptation LARCH, Customization in species models. Statutory Research Tasks Nature and Environment, WOt report 23, available at W:\Gis\Ecotopen. The translation table from ecotopes to sub-ecotopes (Ecotoop-codes.xls) is in exactly that folder.
Buildings	Top10_2006_gebouwdh Top10_2006_ngebouw	Density of buildings in the Netherlands (1 x 1 km)	Based on the TOP10 vector 2006 (https://www.kadaster.nl/-/top10nl)

Using LiDAR to assess the influence of fine-scale habitat structure on the abundance of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*)

<p>Water type</p>	<p>water_brak water_klein_diep water_langz_strom water_meer_diep water_meer_groot water_meer_ondiep water_ondiep_veen water_ondiep_zand water_overgang water_riv_langz water_riv_snel water_rivgeb</p>	<p>Cover with water type 'Brackish waters' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Small deep pools' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Slow flowing river' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Moderate deep lakes' (1x1 km) Coverage with water type 'Great Lakes' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Moderately large shallow lakes' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Small shallow peat lakes' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Small shallow pools (sand, lime)' (1x1 km) Coverage with water type 'Transitional water' (1x1 km) Coverage with water type 'Slow flowing waters' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Fast flowing river' (1x1 km) Cover with water type 'Waters in the river area' (1x1 km)</p>	<p>Based on P.J.T.M. van Puijenbroek and J. Clement (WUR) (2010) Aquatic Base Map\; the Water Type Map, Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, PBL publication number 500067004. A PDF of this document can be found in the folder W:\Gis\water_nl, together with the translation table 'Water types water types map 2009.xls' from Framework Directive Water types to the variable names used for environment variables.</p>
<p>Groundwater table</p>	<p>gvg_mean</p>	<p>Average spring groundwater level (1x1 km)</p>	<p>Based on the groundwater map of the Netherlands https://www.wur.nl/nl/Research-Results/Research-Institutes/Environmental-Research/Facilities-Products/Software-and-models/Groundwater-Dynamics/Maps-Groundwaterdynamics.htm) and the AHN elevation map.</p>
<p>Openness</p>	<p>openheid2009_mean</p>	<p>Openness (average) of the landscape (1x1 km) The openness of the landscape is characterized by the average visible area [ha] on the scale of 1x1 km. This is calculated by determining the sight distance in all directions for each point with a resolution of 100 m and calculating the area over it, maximized at 1520 ha.</p>	<p>The map is based on Meeuwsen HAM and Jochem R (2011) Openness of the landscape; Calculations with the ViewScape model. Wot working document 281. Statutory Research Tasks Nature and Environment, Wageningen. https://docplayer.nl/25648381-Wot-working-documents-openness-of-the-landscape-calculations-with-the-model-viewscape-ham-meeuwsen-r-jochem.html (also available at W:\Gis\scale_landscape\Visible_openness_2009\WOTwerkdocument_281_Openness of the landscape.pdf)</p>
<p>Other data (no specified category)</p>	<p>Riet_area Riet_area_perc Riet_omtrekdh Riet_omtrek SNL_riet SNL_riet_overjarig</p>	<p>Area of reed Percentage of reed area Reed</p>	<p>The layers riet_area, riet_omtrek and riet_omtrekdh are primarily based on the information in the TOP10NL topographic map of The Netherlands. The SNL_riet covariate is based on the location of reedbeds for which management contracts have been issued.</p>

Table 2. All model statistics for model 1 – the SDM run without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics – showing the ten-fold cross validation with statistics for each iteration. MAE = Mean Average Error, MFE = Mean Forecast Error, RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error, corr = Spearman correlation factor, explVar = explained variance. The mean statistics from the cross validation are shown in the bottom row.

Iteration	MAE	MFE	RMSE	corr	R2	intercept	p.intercept	slope	p.slope	explVar
iteration 1	0.193	-0.018	1.531	0.285	0.774	-0.063	0	1.171	0	78.59
iteration 2	0.189	-0.008	1.391	0.302	0.824	-0.001	0.024	0.977	0	76.03
iteration 3	0.178	-0.014	1.32	0.33	0.81	-0.047	0	1.112	0	77.04
iteration 4	0.193	-0.047	1.466	0.296	0.779	-0.008	0.011	0.878	0	78.3
iteration 5	0.169	-0.046	1.274	0.305	0.77	0.008	0.119	0.797	0	78.68
iteration 6	0.169	0.012	1.289	0.317	0.82	-0.022	0.003	1.135	0	78.05
iteration 7	0.16	-0.039	1.018	0.321	0.398	0.028	0	0.662	0	79.02
iteration 8	0.169	-0.01	1.308	0.313	0.671	-0.015	0	1.024	0	79.31
iteration 9	0.149	-0.005	1.143	0.284	0.836	-0.064	0	1.26	0	77.86
iteration 10	0.178	-0.002	1.429	0.295	0.612	0.008	0	0.956	0	79.85
mean	0.175	-0.018	1.317	0.305	0.73	-0.018	0.016	0.997	0	78.27

Table 3. All model statistics for model 2 – the SDM run with the inclusion of LiDAR metrics – showing the ten-fold cross validation with statistics for each iteration. MAE = Mean Average Error, MFE = Mean Forecast Error, RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error, corr = Spearman correlation factor, explVar = explained variance. The mean statistics from the cross validation are shown in the bottom row.

Iteration	MAE	MFE	RMSE	corr	R2	intercept	p.intercept	slope	p.slope	explVar
iteration 1	0.159	-0.016	1.133	0.319	0.564	0.015	0	0.846	0	79.86
iteration 2	0.133	-0.055	0.854	0.346	0.888	-0.028	0.001	0.903	0.562	77.53
iteration 3	0.185	-0.066	1.317	0.339	0.781	0.013	0.204	0.765	0	78.07
iteration 4	0.21	-0.009	1.369	0.348	0.825	-0.045	0	1.107	0	77.5
iteration 5	0.123	-0.041	0.931	0.312	0.778	0	0.054	0.802	0	78.87
iteration 6	0.222	0.034	1.956	0.338	0.783	-0.029	0.003	1.194	0	79.8
iteration 7	0.163	-0.008	1.21	0.327	0.614	-0.008	0	1.002	0	79.41
iteration 8	0.154	0.031	1.241	0.329	0.861	-0.003	0.073	1.132	0	77.75
iteration 9	0.122	-0.055	0.967	0.275	0.57	0	0.003	0.701	0.678	79.37
iteration 10	0.175	-0.006	1.292	0.318	0.835	-0.058	0	1.197	0	77.04
mean	0.165	-0.019	1.227	0.325	0.75	-0.014	0.034	0.965	0.124	78.52

Figure 10. Moran's I graph of the model residuals of the ranger density model 1 which does not include the LiDAR metrics as covariates.

Figure 11. Moran's I graph of the model residuals of the ranger density model 2 which includes the LiDAR metrics as covariates.

Figure 12. Relative variable importance plot (%) for model 1 - run without the inclusion of LiDAR metrics. Displaying the 30 most important variables (y axis) for predicting the relative abundance of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*).

Figure 13. Map showing the LiDAR 1 km predicted density of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands. The map shows a zoomed sample of the predictions in Flevoland and the surrounding area, which includes the Oostvaardersplassen. Legend in the bottom left shows the colour scale for bearded reedling predicted density.

Figure 14. Map showing the LiDAR 250 m predicted density of the bearded reedling in the Netherlands. The map shows a zoomed sample of the predictions in Flevoland and the surrounding area, which includes the Oostvaardersplassen. Legend in the bottom left shows the colour scale for bearded reedling predicted density.

Figure 15. Map showing the recorded presences (red dot) and absences (black dot) of the bearded reedling (*Panurus biarmicus*) in the Netherlands. Data collected from Sovon bird observation methodologies (BMP and Atlas).

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